

INVESTIGATING THE ASSOCIATION BETWEEN ACCOUNTABILITY MECHANISMS AND WHITE-COLLAR CRIMES AMONG CIVIL SERVANTS IN DISTRICT KARAK

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ABSTRACT

The study, titled "Investigating the Association between Accountability Mechanisms and White-Collar Crimes among Civil Servants in District Karak," aimed to examine the weaknesses in the accountability system that contributed to the prevalence of white-collar crimes within selected government departments. Using a cross-sectional quantitative design, data were collected from 217 civil servants through a structured Likert-scale questionnaire, with a reliability coefficient ($\alpha = 0.631$ for accountability and $\alpha = 0.677$ for white-collar crime). Univariate findings showed that 82% of respondents believed weak accountability encouraged corruption, 83% agreed that strong accountability promoted honesty and efficiency, and 82% cited political interference as a major barrier to fair enforcement. The relationship between the variables was tested by applying the Chi-Square test and Tau-C statistics. The results reveal significant associations between accountability indicators and white-collar crimes, particularly political interference ($\chi^2 = 36.917$; $p = 0.000$; $\text{Tau-C} = 0.142$), weak monitoring and auditing ($\chi^2 = 19.131$; $p = 0.002$; $\text{Tau-C} = 0.102$), absence of performance evaluation ($\chi^2 = 18.866$; $p = 0.001$; $\text{Tau-C} = 0.136$), and inadequate whistleblowing mechanisms ($\chi^2 = 12.865$; $p = 0.012$; $\text{Tau-C} = 0.128$). The results confirmed that politically influenced, selective, and poorly monitored accountability systems lead to the misuse of authority and resource mismanagement. The study concluded that depoliticizing oversight institutions, improving auditing systems, enforcing whistleblower protections, and introducing regular performance evaluations are vital to curbing white-collar crimes among civil servants in District Karak.

Keywords: Accountability Mechanisms, White-Collar Crime, Civil Servants, Political Interference, Performance Evaluation, District Karak, Pakistan.

INTRODUCTION

There are many types of crimes found in every society. These crimes may be in the form of violent crimes, property crimes, business-related frauds,

embezzlement, money laundering, bribery and corruption, tax evasion, identity theft, insider trading, pyramid and Ponzi schemes, and false

advertising (Karthek & Bala, 2023; Kratcoski, 2018). Among these, one of the most important is white-collar crime. First introduced by Edwin Sutherland, the concept of white-collar crime refers to non-violent, financially motivated offences committed by individuals in positions of trust and authority (Sutherland, 1983).

In white-collar crime, civil servants, particularly those in the public sector, may engage in acts such as bribery, embezzlement, misappropriation of public resources, and abuse of authority. These violations pose a serious threat to institutional integrity, public trust, and effective governance, particularly in developing countries like Pakistan, where accountability systems are often weak or politicized (Cheema et al., 2024). Despite the presence of legal frameworks, white-collar crimes persist within the civil services, undermining efficiency and service delivery.

OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY

To test the association between accountability mechanisms and white-collar crimes.

HYPOTHESIS OF THE STUDY

H₁: There is a significant association between accountability mechanisms and white-collar crimes among civil servants in District Karak.

H₀: There is no significant association between accountability mechanisms and white-collar crimes among civil servants in District Karak.

Tab-1 PROPORTIONAL ALLOCATION OF SAMPLE RESPONDENTS

S.No.	Stratum	Total	Sample
1	District Education Office (Male & Female)	120	89
2	Social Welfare Department	18	13
3	District Accounts Office	32	24
4	Food Department	33	25
5	Communication and Works (C&W) Office	90	67
Total		293	217

Source: District Account Office Karak, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa (2025).

DATA COLLECTION PRE-TESTING, RELIABILITY, AND VALIDITY OF THE TOOLS

The primary data was collected through a structured questionnaire, covering both independent and dependent variables of the study.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Nature of the Study, Study Design, and Universe of the Study

This study was quantitative in nature, where data were analysed using frequencies and percentages, and the associations between variables were examined using the Chi-square test. Further, cross-sectional research design, both in time consideration and visit to the field for the collection of primary information, as recommended by was followed (Babbie, 1989; Creswell, 2014). Also, this study was conducted in District Karak, located in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa (KP), Pakistan. Further, based on the objectives of the study, the universe was limited to the District Administration Offices of District Karak only.

SAMPLING PROCEDURES

Based on the main objectives of the study, the data were collected from civil servants in the District of Karak. However, due to easy accessibility and relevance, five departments were selected as the study population, including the district education office (Male & Female), social welfare department, district accounts office, food department and communication and works (C&W) office constituted the study population. The total number of civil servants and their proportional allocation have been given in the table below.

The response of the respondents was noted through a three-level Likert scale of agree, neutral, and disagree. Before the actual data collection, the structured questionnaire was pre-tested with a small group of the target population to identify

ambiguities or inconsistencies. Based on the findings from this pilot survey, necessary changes were made to improve clarity and accuracy. Further, after collecting primary information, the responses were passed through a reliability test using Cronbach's Alpha in SPSS. According to Ghazali (2008), a Cronbach's Alpha value of 0.6 or above is considered acceptable for internal consistency, while 0.8 or above indicates a high level of reliability. In this study, the overall reliability coefficient for the accountability mechanism was found to be 0.631 and for white-collar crime (0.677), confirming the reliability and validity of the tool and its projection for further statistical analysis. Moreover, the questionnaire was validated through face validity, content validity, as well as construct validity following established procedures to guarantee comprehensive coverage of the study's key variables and conceptual dimensions (Smith, 1991).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The data collected was coded, tabulated, and entered into the Statistical Packages for the Social Sciences (SPSS version 2022) for analysis. The data were analyzed by applying univariate and bivariate data analysis one by one to meet the research objective. The univariate analysis comprised the computation of frequencies and percentages calculations of the independent variable, while the bi-variate analysis included the association between accountability mechanism and white-collar crime in the study population through Chi-square statistics, where the Tau-C test was applied additionally. Lastly, all the results were discussed briefly and explained with relevant literature of the study.

FREQUENCY AND PERCENTAGE DISTRIBUTION

The analysis revealed that weak accountability structures and a lack of transparency are major facilitators of white-collar crimes. Most respondents strongly agreed that ineffective auditing, political interference, and the absence of fair evaluation contribute to corruption. Conversely, they believed that robust accountability mechanisms foster honesty and

efficiency. The section on accountability mechanisms explored respondents' perceptions of the effectiveness of accountability systems in preventing corruption within government departments. The responses are summarized in the table below.

The results indicate that the majority of respondents, 177 (82%), agreed that weak accountability mechanisms encourage civil servants to engage in corruption, while only 18 respondents (8%) remained neutral and 22 (10%) disagreed. This finding suggests that ineffective accountability frameworks significantly contribute to corrupt practices. Similarly, 138 (64%) agreed that monitoring and auditing systems in government offices are ineffective, whereas 46 (21%) were neutral and 33 (15%) disagreed. This indicates perceived deficiencies in internal control and auditing mechanisms. In response to the statement "Does fear of detection and punishment reduce corrupt practices?", 169 (78%) agreed, confirming that the presence of strong deterrents discourages unethical conduct.

Furthermore, 154 (71%) of respondents agreed that anti-corruption institutions lack independence and effectiveness, while 35 (16%) were neutral and 28 (13%) disagreed. This demonstrates scepticism toward institutional integrity and political autonomy. A substantial majority, 178 (82%), also believed that political interference undermines accountability measures, whereas 16 (7%) were neutral and 23 (11%) disagreed. This highlights the perceived political influence that obstructs transparent governance. Regarding transparency in decision-making, 145 (67%) agreed that it reduces the likelihood of white-collar crime, 39 (18%) were neutral, and 33 (15%) disagreed.

Thus, transparency is viewed as a key preventive measure.

When asked whether accountability processes are selective and biased, 117 (54%) agreed, 49 (23%) remained neutral, and 51 (23%) disagreed, indicating a divided opinion on fairness in accountability practices. Moreover, 140 (65%) of respondents agreed that whistleblowing mechanisms are insufficient to discourage corruption, while 51 (23%) were neutral and 26 (12%) disagreed. This emphasizes the need for

stronger employee protection systems. Regarding the absence of performance evaluation, 173 (80%) agreed that it encourages misuse of resources, 29 (13%) were neutral, and 15 (7%) disagreed. The data imply that a lack of performance accountability promotes inefficiency and corruption. Finally, a strong consensus, 181 (83%), agreed that strong accountability systems promote honesty and efficiency, while 23 (11%) were neutral and 13 (6%) disagreed. These findings collectively indicate that robust accountability frameworks are essential for minimizing white-collar crimes among civil servants.

DISCUSSION

The primary information strongly indicates that weak accountability mechanisms, ineffective monitoring, poor and biased audit, lack of punishment, passive role of anti-corruption agencies, and the public sector framework have lost trust and confidence among the general masses of the country. White-collar crime is a global issue and requires collective efforts and moral implications for eradication. All this

information is strongly supported by the research work of Shima (2017). According to this research work, the anti-corruption efforts have no more practical implications and are just limited to slogans and offices. Likewise, many other causes have fostered corruption in bureaucratic and top management and establishment wings of the nation. The people there always prepare their personal and financial development instead of public interest. Consequently, social injustice is inevitable, where desperation grows in the general masses, further leading to misconduct, breach of law, poor institutional performance, boycott, and civil war between the state and its citizens. Further, it leaves citizens susceptible to crime and radicalization, both as perpetrators and as victims. The research shows that white-collar crime not dealt with effectively will inevitably lead to skirmish and unpredictability, and as a result, it directly and indirectly hits government agencies at local and country levels, but around the world, as fragile or failed states become fertile breeding grounds for insurgency, terrorism, and organized crime (Asgedom, 2021).

Table II: Frequency and Percentage Distribution of Accountability Mechanisms

S#	Statement	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Total
1	Weak accountability mechanisms encourage civil servants to engage in corruption.	177(82)	18(8)	22(10)	217(100)
2	Monitoring and auditing systems in government offices are ineffective.	138(64)	46(21)	33(15)	217(100)
3	Fear of detection and punishment reduces corrupt practices.	169(78)	29(13)	19(9)	217(100)
4	The anti-corruption institutions lack independence and effectiveness.	154(71)	35(16)	28(13)	217(100)
5	Political interference undermines accountability measures.	178(82)	16(7)	23(11)	217(100)
6	Transparency in decision-making reduces the likelihood of white-collar crime.	145(67)	39(18)	33(15)	217(100)
7	Civil servants believe accountability processes are selective and biased.	117(54)	49(23)	51(23)	217(100)
8	Whistleblowing mechanisms are insufficient to encourage employees to report corruption or misconduct.	140(65)	51(23)	26(12)	217(100)
9	Absence of performance evaluation encourages misuse of resources.	173(80)	29(13)	15(7)	217(100)
10	Strong accountability systems promote honesty and efficiency.	181(83)	23(11)	13(6)	217(100)

Association Between Independent Variable Accountability Mechanisms and Dependent Variable White-Collar Crimes

In this section, the independent variable accountability mechanisms were analyzed to determine their relationship with the dependent variable, white-collar crimes among civil servants. The purpose was to understand how the quality and enforcement of accountability systems influence the likelihood of corruption and unethical conduct within government institutions. The results reveal varying degrees of association, ranging from highly significant to non-significant, depending on the specific accountability-related statement.

The first statement that “weak accountability mechanisms encourage civil servants to engage in corruption” shows a highly significant and direct association with white-collar crimes ($\chi^2 = 31.03$; $P = 0.000$), Tau-C (0.125; 0.002). All these primary results support the research work of (Khan, 2018). Khan is of the view that insufficient accountability and poor oversight systems are major contributors to unethical activities among civil servants. When monitoring bodies fail to operate effectively, officials perceive low risks of punishment, leading to increased corruption. Furthermore, monitoring and auditing systems in government offices are ineffective, also demonstrating a significant association ($\chi^2 = 19.131$; $P = 0.002$), Tau-C (0.102; 0.016). This result highlights that ineffective auditing processes and weak internal control mechanisms create administrative loopholes that can be exploited by employees for personal gain. It implies that regular, transparent auditing can play a decisive role in reducing white-collar misconduct. In addition, the fear of detection and punishment reduces corrupt practices, presents a significant relationship ($\chi^2 = 15.317$; $P = 0.004$), and Tau-C (0.071; 0.068). This finding affirms that when the probability of detection and the severity of punishment increase, civil servants are less likely to engage in corrupt practices. The fear of accountability thus acts as a psychological deterrent factor against misconduct (Akhter & Liu, 2018).

On the other hand, “anti-corruption institutions lack independence and effectiveness” yields a non-significant result ($\chi^2 = 7.844$; $P = 0.097$), Tau-C

(0.160; 0.149). Although respondents agreed that anti-corruption institutions face political and administrative limitations, the statistical association was not strong enough to establish a direct link with white-collar crime levels. This may suggest that while institutional weakness exists, employees might perceive other factors, like political interference or workplace culture, as more influential (Johnston, 2014). Moreover, political interference undermines accountability measures, displaying a highly significant association ($\chi^2 = 36.917$; $P = 0.000$), Tau-C (0.142; 0.001). This strong result shows that political influence severely disrupts fair accountability systems, allowing corrupt officials to evade scrutiny. It reinforces the argument that political neutrality is essential for enforcing transparent and consistent accountability in public administration. In contrast, transparency reducing white-collar crime is non-significant ($\chi^2 = 4.688$; $P = 0.321$), Tau-C (0.056; 0.190). This means that although transparency is theoretically important, respondents may not directly link open decision-making processes with lower corruption, possibly due to weak enforcement of transparency mechanisms in practice (Bauhr & Grimes, 2014; Mungiu-Pippidi, 2013).

Similarly, “civil servants believe that accountability processes are selective and biased” reveals a significant association ($\chi^2 = 13.321$; $P = 0.010$), Tau-C (0.130; 0.007). This information is strongly in line with the research work of Kolstad & Wiig (2009), indicating that when accountability is perceived as unequal or politically motivated, employees lose trust in the system, which may increase tolerance for corruption and unethical practices. Additionally, whistleblowing mechanisms are insufficient is significantly associated ($\chi^2 = 12.865$; $P = 0.012$), Tau-C (0.128; 0.005). This emphasizes that ineffective whistleblower protection discourages employees from exposing wrongdoing, allowing corruption to persist. Encouraging and safeguarding whistleblowers can thus strengthen accountability. Finally, “the absence of performance evaluation encourages misuse of resources” also shows a significant and positive association ($\chi^2 = 18.866$; $P = 0.001$), Tau-C (0.136; 0.001). This finding implies that when civil servants are not regularly

evaluated on performance and ethical behavior, there is more room for inefficiency and misuse of public funds (DeWeaver, 2020). In conclusion, the results of Table I collectively demonstrate that weak accountability mechanisms, political interference, ineffective monitoring, and biased evaluation systems are

strongly and significantly linked to white-collar crimes among civil servants in District Karak. Effective, transparent, and impartial accountability processes are therefore essential to control corruption and uphold integrity in public service.

Table III: Association Between Accountability Mechanism and White-Collar Crimes

Statement	Attitude	Accountability Mechanism and White Colour Crime			Total	Chi-square (χ^2) P value
		High Level	Moderate Level	Low Level		
Weak accountability mechanisms encourage civil servants to engage in corruption.	Agree	145	2	27	174	$\chi^2=31.03$ (P=0.000) Tau-C 0.125 (0.002)
	Neutral	18	1	9	28	
	Disagree	6	1	8	15	
Monitoring and auditing systems in government offices are ineffective.	Agree	112	1	20	133	$\chi^2=19.131$ (P=0.002) Tau-C =0.102 (0.016)
	Neutral	31	3	14	48	
	Disagree	26	3	7	36	
Fear of detection and punishment reduces corrupt practices.	Agree	134	2	28	164	$\chi^2=15.317$ (P=0.004) Tau-C =0.071 (0.068)
	Neutral	17	11	14	32	
	Disagree	18	1	2	21	
Anti-corruption institutions lack independence and effectiveness?	Agree	123	22	28	153	$\chi^2=7.844$ (P=0.097) Tau-C =0.160 (0.149)
	Neutral	25	4	8	37	
	Disagree	17	2	8	27	
Political interference undermines accountability measures.	Agree	148	2	28	178	$\chi^2=36.917$ (P=0.000) Tau-C=0.142 (0.001)
	Neutral	14	1	1	16	
	Disagree	7	1	15	23	
Transparency in decision-making reduces the likelihood of white-collar crime.	Agree	111	3	23	137	$\chi^2=4.688$ (P=0.321) Tau-C =.056 (0.190)
	Neutral	33	3	11	47	
	Disagree	25	1	7	33	
Civil servants believe accountability processes are selective and biased?	Agree	96	2	17	115	$\chi^2=13.321$ (P=0.010) Tau-C =0.130 (0.007)
	Neutral	41	1	7	49	
	Disagree	32	1	20	53	
The whistleblowing mechanism is insufficient to encourage employees to report corruption or misconduct	Agree	117	3	20	140	$\chi^2=12.865$ (P=0.012) Tau-C=0.128 (0.005)
	Neutral	40	1	4	45	
	Disagree	12	2	10	24	

Absence of performance evaluation encourages misuse of resources.	Agree	145	2	27	174	$\chi^2=18.866$ (P=0.001) Tau-C=0.136 (0.001)
	Neutral	18	1	9	28	
	Disagree	6	1	8	15	

CONCLUSION

The study concludes that weak accountability mechanisms, ineffective monitoring, and politically influenced oversight systems significantly contribute to white-collar crimes among civil servants in District Karak. The findings show that factors such as poor auditing, lack of performance evaluation, and limited whistleblowing protections create an environment where misuse of authority and resource mismanagement can flourish. Political interference emerged as a major barrier, disrupting fair enforcement and weakening institutional integrity. Although transparency and institutional independence were acknowledged as important, they displayed weaker statistical associations, reflecting gaps between policy and practice. Overall, the results highlight the need for impartial, transparent, and well-enforced accountability frameworks to promote honesty, efficiency, and ethical conduct within public service.

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